

Synthesis of 2-(2, 4-Dichlorophenoxy methyl)-5-Mercapto Acetyl- (aryl/alkyl substituted) urea-1,3,4-Oxadiazoles and their Biological Activity

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Fifteen new 2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy methyl)-5-mercaptoacetyl (aryl/alkyl substituted) urea-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been synthesised and their antibacterial activities evaluated.

N-CHLOROACETYL phenyl urea have shown fungicidal and bactericidal activity¹. Various oxadiazolyl compounds have been reported as insecticides, miticides and bactericides^{2,3}. Antibacterial and Fungicidal properties have been exhibited by various urea derivatives⁴⁻⁷. Anticholinesterase activity of esters of N-chloroacetyl ureas were observed by Sen Gupta *et al*⁸. In view of these observations it was considered of interest to synthesise a series of 2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy methyl)-5-mercaptoacetyl (aryl/alkyl substituted) urea-1,3,4-oxadiazoles for biological screening.

chloroacetyl phenyl ureas were synthesised by the method of Jacobs¹⁰.

2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy methyl) 1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thione (i) :

Method of Young¹¹ was used. A suspension of 0.1 mole of 2,4-dichlorophenoxy acetic acid hydrazide, 0.1 mole of potassium hydroxide and 0.11 mole of carbon disulphide was refluxed on steam bath for 8 hr. The reaction mixture cooled, solvent distilled off and residue dissolved in water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. Solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol^a. M.P. 147°. Analysis Calc. for C₉H₆Cl₂N₂O₂S : C, 38.98%; H, 2.17%; N, 10.11%. Found : C, 38.82%; H, 2.12%; N, 10.24%.

2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy methyl)-5-mercaptoacetyl (aryl/alkyl substituted) urea 1,3,4-oxadiazoles :

To a suspension of 2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazolin-5-thione (0.01 mole) in 50 ml. of dry benzene and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.02 mole) was added the N-chloroacetylphenyl/alkyl urea. Reaction mixture refluxed for 8 hr. Then benzene distilled off and residue crystallised from suitable solvent such as ethanol. The analysis, m.ps. and other pertinent data are recorded in Table 1.

Biological Data

All compounds of Table 1 were screened for their inhibitory effects against *E. Coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus magaterium* by agar diffusion technique¹². Compound numbers 2, 3, 7, 8, 13, 14 and 15 have inhibited the growth of *E. coli*. Four compounds (2, 6, 8, 11) showed inhibition against *Bacillus magaterium*. Inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus* was observed in four compounds (8, 13, 14, 15). Five compounds (8, 9, 11, 12, 15) inhibited the growth of *Salmonella typhosa*.

The compounds described in this article were prepared by the condensation of I and substituted N-chloroacetyl phenyl alkyl urea in dry benzene in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are not corrected. Infrared Spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer in KBr. Bacterial cultures maintained at C.D.R.I., Lucknow were used for biological studies.

Substituted phenylureas were prepared from potassium isocyanate and amine⁹. Corresponding N-

^a IR : 3200(NH), 1600(C=N), 1320(C=S), 1480(C-NH)Cm⁻¹.

TABLE I—2-(2, 4-DICHLOROPHENOXYMETHYL)-5-MERCAPTOACE-
TYL-(ARYL/ALKYL SUBSTITUTED)
UREA-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLES II

Comp. No. ^a	R	M.P. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	197	68
2.	2-tolyl	238	60
3.	3-tolyl	224	50
4.	4-tolyl	189	52
5.	2-chloro phenyl	186	55
6.	3-chloro phenyl	213-214	50
7.	4-chloro phenyl	198-199	60
8.	2-methoxy phenyl	212-213	60
9.	4-methoxy phenyl	190-92	60
10.	2-ethoxy phenyl	197-198	56
11.	4-ethoxy phenyl	224-225	66
12.	2-ethyl phenyl	161-162	52
13.	4-bromo phenyl	200-201	64
14.	Methyl	192-193	70
15.	Ethyl	185-186	74

^a Satisfactory elemental analysis have been obtained and found to be within the range.

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